

Molecular Mapping of Enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* Strains in Human, Animal and Water Samples in Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18439119>

Article Received 15-12-2025 / Article Accepted 16-01-2026 / Article Published 18-01-2026

ABSTRACT:

Enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (EPEC) are a leading cause of diarrhea among children globally. This study, carried out from May to June, 2025, applied molecular techniques to investigate the prevalence and antibiotics sensitivity profiles of EPEC in cow dung, human and water samples from Okigwe zone, Imo State, Nigeria. Out of the 50 samples collected in each case, *E. coli* was isolated from 12 cow dung samples (24.00%), 13 river water samples (26.00%) and 15 human faecal samples (30.00%). The phylogenetic tree revealed that the 16S rRNA sequence from some of the isolates produced an exact match during the megablast search for highly similar sequences from the NCBI non-redundant nucleotide (nr/nt) database. The highest percentage of sensitivity of isolates from the three samples was recorded with Ciprofloxacin. Only 41.7% for cow dung, 23.1% for river water and 26.7% for human diarrheal samples were the highest percentage of sensitive isolates recorded with Ciprofloxacin. The isolates were resistant to Augmentin, Ceftriaxone, Cefepime, Aztreonam and Meropenem. All the three studied β -lactamase resistance enzymes including CTX-M, TEM-1 and SHV-1 were expressed by the isolates. The prevalence of CTX-M and SHV-1 enzymes was highest in isolates from human diarrheal samples, with 38.5% and 23.1%, respectively. The prevalence of *eae* and *bfpA* genes of EPEC was highest in isolates from both river water and human diarrheal samples, which equally recorded 30.8% and 38.5% prevalence respectively. These results require immediate heightened to mitigate the spread of multidrug resistant EPEC through application of contaminated human and animal dungs.

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How to Cite

Ohalete, Chinyere Ngozi, Nnagbo, Pauline, Anyanwu, Gladys Onyenonachi, K. M. C. U. J. C. O. C. E. Y. K. A. . (2026). Molecular Mapping of Enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* Strains in Human, Animal and Water Samples in Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, 7(01), 33-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18439119>

Keywords: Diarrhoeal diseases, Enteropathogenic *E. coli*, Public health, *E. coli* pathotypes, Child mortality

1. INTRODUCTION:

Diarrheal illnesses are a major public health concern, particularly in poor countries, resulting in significant morbidity and mortality in children under five years old (Okeke et al., 2000). In 2017, diarrhea was projected to account for around 8% of all fatalities among children under the age of five worldwide. This translates to over 1,300 young children dying per day, or around 480,000 children per year, despite the availability of a simple medical solution (UNICEF, 2020).

Escherichia coli are thought to be ubiquitous microbial commensals of both humans and warm-blooded animals. However, some strains have been identified as having the ability to cause both intestinal and extra-intestinal diseases (Scheutz et al., 2011). *E. coli* are facultative anaerobic bacilli with a Gram-negative characteristic. They lack glomeruli and rely on peritrichous flagellation for motility. These bacteria are thought to be potential causes of a variety of disorders, including pneumonia, septicemia, cystitis, urinary tract infections, cholecystitis, newborn meningitis, pyelonephritis, and infections of the central nervous system and respiratory tract (Makvana & Krilov, 2015). However, it is important to note that many *E. coli* strains are commensal flora residing in the gut, and the equilibrium between bacterial capacity to acquire viral factor and host immune status primarily determines the barrier between *E. coli* symbiosis and virulence (Heng et al., 2015).

Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC) is a leading cause of diarrhoea in newborns in impoverished countries (Al-Hilali and Almohana, 2011; Abba & Dutsinma, 2021). EPEC pathogenesis is based on bacteria's close adhesion to intestinal epithelium cells, which results in the formation of lesions known as "attaching and effacing" (A/E) lesions (Mohammadzadeh et al., 2013; Abba & Dutsinma, 2021). The distribution of virulence factors found

in various *E. coli* pathotypes, including Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), will provide significant insights into the mechanisms by which various *E. coli* strains cause disease and result in the growth of different *E. coli* types (Almanseekanaa, 2022).

E. coli is frequently identified among diarrhoeic children in Imo State, Nigeria, but its serological and molecular parameters are not usually investigated. Therefore, the rate of diarrhoea caused by EPEC remains unknown. Furthermore, there is a lack of research into the prevalence of EPEC in animal manure and environmental samples in Imo State. This study then evaluated the prevalence of EPEC as a cause of infectious diarrhoea in cow dung, human diarrheal faeces, and water samples from the Okigwe zone of Imo State, Nigeria, as well as their antibiotic susceptibility pattern, to give baseline data for epidemiological control.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS:

2.1 Study Area

This study was conducted in Okigwe zone of Imo State, Nigeria. Imo State is a state in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, bordered to the north by Anambra State, Rivers State to the west and south, and Abia State to the east. Agriculture is the principal occupation of the inhabitants, although over-farming and high population density have severely deteriorated the land (Onu et al. 2008). In Okigwe zone, the rainy season starts in April and lasts until October, with annual rainfall ranging from 1,500 to 2,200 mm (60 to 80 inches). An average annual temperature of over 20 °C (68.0 °F) results in 75% relative humidity. During the rainy season, humidity can approach 90% (Njoku et al., 2017). Harmattan occurs for two months during the dry season, from late December to late February. The hottest months are January through March (Okoroafor-Nwosu et al., 2017).

2.2 Samples Collection

The collection of samples for the isolation of *E. coli* was evenly distributed across Okigwe zone of Imo State. A total of 150 samples comprising of 50 samples of each of cow dungs (C) from abattoirs and cow rearing spots, human diarrheal stools from children between 0 to 5 years (H), and water samples from rivers (W) were randomly collected from the study area using sterile sample containers. Samples were collected from May to June, 2025. Each sample was labelled, preserved in ice pack and transported to the laboratory for immediate analyses.

2.3 Biochemical Characterization of Isolates

E. coli was isolated using Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar which was prepared as directed by the manufacturer. Prior to inoculation, collected samples were serially diluted under aseptic conditions. Then 1 ml of 10^{-5} dilution was inoculated by spreading on the media and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Each discrete colony was sub-cultured by streaking on fresh media to obtain pure cultures. The isolated microorganisms were characterized using morphological, biochemical and molecular methods. Gram staining and biochemical characterization of isolates were done following the method of Cheesbrough (2004) and Aryal (2020).

2.4 Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

The chemotherapeutic agents; gentamicin (GEN), meropenem (MEM), levofloxacin (LBC), augmentin (AUG), ceftriazone (CTR), ciprofloxacin (CIP}, cefepime (CPM), and aztreonam (AT) were tested against the isolates using Kirby Bauer disc diffusion method as described by Hudzicki (2016). A cell suspension of the inocula equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standard was employed.

2.5 Molecular Characterization of EPEC Isolates

2.5.1 Extraction of DNA

Extraction was done using a ZR fungi/bacteria DNA mini prep extraction kit supplied by Inqaba South Africa. Pure colonies of the bacterial isolate were transferred into 200 µl of isotonic buffer in a ZR Bashing Bead lysis tubes and 750 µl of lysis solution was added to the tube. The tubes were secured in a bead beater fitted with a 2 ml tube holder assembly and processed at maximum speed for 5 min. The ZR bashing bead lysis tubes were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 1 min. Then 400 µl of supernatant were transferred to a Zymo-Spin IV spin filter (orange top) in a collection tube, and centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 1 min. Then 1200 µl of fungal/bacterial DNA binding buffer was added to the filtrate in the collection tubes, bringing the final volume to 1600 µl. Subsequently, 800 µl was transferred to a Zymo-Spin IIC column in a collection tube, centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 1 min and the flow through was discarded from the collection tube. The remaining volume was transferred to the same Zymo-spin and spun. Two hundred (200 µl) microliter of the DNA Pre-Was buffer was added to the Zymo-spin IIC in a new collection tube and spun at 10,000 rpm for 1 min followed by the addition of 500 µl of fungal/bacterial DNA Wash Buffer and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 1 min. The Zymo-spin IIC column was transferred to a clean 1500 µl centrifuge tube, 100 µl of DNA elution buffer was added to the column matrix and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 sec to elute the DNA. The ultra-pure DNA was then stored at -20 °C for other downstream reaction.

2.5.2 DNA quantification

The extracted genomic DNA was quantified using the Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer. The software of the equipment was lunched by double clicking on the Nanodrop icon. The equipment was initialized with 2 µl of sterile distilled water and blanked using normal saline. Then 2 µl of the

extracted DNA was loaded onto the lower pedestal, the upper pedestal was brought down to contact the extracted DNA on the lower pedestal. The DNA concentration was measured by clicking on the “measure” button.

2.6 Extended Spectrum Beta- Lactamases detection

2.6.1 Amplification of TEM genes

TEM genes from the isolates were amplified using the TEMF: 5'-ATGAGTATTCAACATTTCCGTG-3' and TEMR: 5'-TTACCAATGCTTAATCAGTGAG-3' primers on an ABI 9700 Applied Biosystems thermal cycler at a final volume of 40 microlitres for 35 cycles. The PCR mix included: the X2 Dream Taq Master mix supplied by Inqaba, South Africa (Taq polymerase, DNTPs, MgCl), the primers at a concentration of 0.4M and 50 ng of the extracted DNA as template. The PCR conditions were as follows: Initial denaturation, 95 °C for 5 minutes; denaturation, 95°C for 30 seconds; annealing, 58 °C for 30 seconds; extension, 72 °C for 30 seconds for 35 cycles and final extension, 72 °C for 5 minutes. The product was resolved on a 1% agarose gel at 120V for 25 minutes and visualized on a UV transilluminator.

2.6.2 Amplification of CTX-M genes

CTX-M genes from the isolates were amplified using the CTX-MF: 5'-CGCTTTGCGATGTGCAG-3' and CTX-MR:5'-ACCGCGATATCGTTGGT-3' primers on a ABI 9700 Applied Biosystems thermal cycler at a final volume of 40 µl for 35 cycles. The PCR mix included: the X2 Dream Taq Master mix supplied by Inqaba, South Africa (Taq polymerase, DNTPs, MgCl), the primers at a concentration of 0.4M and 50 ng of the extracted DNA as template. The PCR conditions were as follows: Initial denaturation, 95 °C for 5 min; denaturation, 95 °C for 30 sec; annealing, 52 °C for 30 sec; extension, 72 °C for 30 sec for 35 cycles and final extension, 72 °C for 5

min. The product was resolved on a 1% agarose gel at 120V for 25 min and visualized on a UV transilluminator.

2.6.3 Amplification of SHV genes

SHV genes from the isolates were amplified using the SHV F: 5' CGCCTGTGTATTATCTCCCT-3' and SHV R: 5'-CGAGTAGTCCACCAGATCCT-3' primers on an ABI 9700 Applied Biosystems thermal cycler at a final volume of 30 µl for 35 cycles. The PCR mix included: the X2 Dream Taq Master mix supplied by Inqaba, South Africa (Taq polymerase, DNTPs, MgCl), the primers at a concentration of 0.4M and 50 ng of the extracted DNA as template. The PCR conditions were as follows: Initial denaturation, 95 °C for 5 min; denaturation, 95 °C for 30 sec; annealing, 56 °C for 40 sec; extension, 72 °C for 50 sec for 35 cycles and final extension, 72 °C for 5 min. The product was resolved on a 1% agarose gel at 120V for 25 min and visualized on a UV transilluminator.

2.7 Molecular Identification of Isolates

2.7.1 DNA Extraction (Heat Method)

Five millilitres of an overnight broth culture of the bacteria isolate in Luria Bertani (LA) media centrifuged) at 14000 rpm for 3 min in 1.5 ml Eppendorf tubes. The supernatant was discarded and the cells were re-suspended in 500 µl of normal saline. It was vortexed to dislodge residue and homogenized. It is centrifuged for 3 min and supernatant discarded again and 300 µl of DNA elution buffer was added. It was vortexed and placed on heating block at 95 °C for 20 min. The heated bacterial suspension was fast cooled on ice and spun for 3 min at 1400 rpm for purification. About 200 µl of the supernatant containing the DNA was transferred to 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tube and stored at -20 °C for other downstream reactions.

2.7.2 DNA Quantification

The extracted genomic DNA was quantified using the Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer. The software of the equipment was launched by double clicking on the Nanodrop Icon. The equipment was initialized with 2 µl of sterile distilled water and blanked using normal saline. The 2 µl of extracted DNA was loaded onto the lower pedestal. The upper pedestal was brought down to contact the extracted DNA on the lower pedestal. The DNA concentration was measured by clicking on the measure button.

2.7.3 16S rRNA Amplification

The 16srRNA regions of the rRNA genes of the isolates were amplified using 27F: 51-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3' and 1492R: 51 CGGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3' primers on a ABI 9700 Applied Biosystem Thermal Cycler at a final volume of 40 µl for 35 cycles. The PCR mix include: the X2 Dream Taq Master mix supplied by Inqaba, South Africa (Taq Polymerase, DNTPs, Mgcl), the primers at a concentration of 0.4 µl and the extracted DNA as template. The PCR conditions were as follows: initial denaturation, 95 °C for 5 min; annealing, 52 °C for 30 sec; extension, 72°C for 30 sec for 35 cycles and final extension, 72 °C for 5 min. The product was resolved on a 1% agarose gel at 130V for 25 min and visualized on a blue light transilluminator. The PCR product is determined by comparing them with 100 bp ladder marker (Amersham Pharmacia Biotech, USA).

2.7.4 Sequencing

Sequencing was done using the big dye terminator kit on a 3510ABI sequencer by Inqaba Biotechnology, Pretoria South Africa. The sequencing was done at a final volume of 10 µl, the components included 0.25 µl big dye terminator v1.1/v3.1, 2.25 µl of 5 x big dye sequencing buffer, 10 µml primer PCR primer, and 2-10 ng PCR template per 100 bp. The sequencing conditions were as follows: 32 cycles of 96 °C for 10 sec, 55 °C for 5 sec and 60 °C for 4 min.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics of Isolates

Table 1 presents the morphological and biochemical characteristics of the targeted *E. coli* isolates obtained from cow dung, river water samples and human diarrheal samples from Okigwe zone of Imo State. These revealed that the isolates were Gram negative rods under light microscope. They were majorly motile, with positive reactions for indole, catalase, and methyl red tests, but negative reactions for oxidase, coagulase, hydrogen sulphide, urease, voges-proskauere, and citrate tests. There was yellow colour on triple sugar iron agar medium which showed their capability for gas production. Results showed that out of a total of 150 samples studied, which comprised of 50 cow dung samples, 50 river water samples and 50 diarrheal samples of children between 0 to 5 years, *E. coli* was isolated from a total of 40 samples representing 26.67% of the total. This gives a total of 73.33% *E. coli* negative samples. Specifically, there was *E. coli* in 12 cow dung samples (24.00%), 13 river water samples (26.00%) and 15 human faecal samples (30.00%) out of the total of 50 samples in each case from Okigwe zone of Imo State. In a related study, results showed that out of 200 faeces collected from an abattoir in Zaria, Nigeria, 183 (91.5%) yielded *E. coli*-like colonies on EMB, 152 (76%) were confirmed as *E. coli* using biochemical assays, and 25 (12.5%) tested positive for Enzyme Immunoassay (EIA) (Kabiru et al., 2015). Another study comprising 150 fresh faecal samples from symptomatic domestic animals (sheep, cattle, and goats) found that the overall diarrhoeal pathogen detection rate was highest in sheep (41.1%), followed by goats (35.5%) and cattle (33.3%). The most common enteric pathogen found in animals (38.7%) was diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* (DEC), with EPEC accounting for 14.7% of the total. They also discovered that sheep (41.7%) were slightly

more infected with DEC than goats (35.5%) and cattle (33.3%) (Shrivastava et al., 2020).

3.2 Molecular Characteristics of *E. coli* Isolates

The phylogenetic tree in Figure 1 shows that H₁ and H₇₂ have no genetic relationship. Also, the MN, MK, KC and OZ have their accession numbers not yet deposited with the NCBI. The tree also suggests that MK have some genetic relationship with H₇₂, C₁₁, W₁₆, C₁₂₈, W₁₁₁, H₁₁₅ and W₉₂. There is possible genetic relationship between C₁₁ W₁₆, C₆₄, C₁₂₈, W₁₁₁, H₇₂, H₁₁₅ and

W₉₂. Following the tree, it suggests some relationship between MK, C₁₁, W₁₆ and C₆₄. It also shows genetic relationship between H₇₂, H₁₁₅ and W₉₂. H₁ and H₂₄ suggests the same organism with 100% relatedness showing no genetic difference. MN is suggested to be related to H₂₄ but not the same with 85.4% relatedness. At 87.8%, H₂₄ connects to MK. C₁₁ is 100% related to KC, OZ, W₁₆, C₆₄, C₁₂₈, W₁₁₁, H₇₂, H₁₁₆, W₉₂. MK is 85.4% related to MN while H₁ and H₂₄ are the parent organisms.

Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree showing the evolutionary relationships between bacterial isolates

Table 1. Morphological and biochemical characteristics of *E. coli* isolates from animal, human and environmental samples

	Gram Stain	Mot. Test	Catal. Test	Cit. Test	Ind. Test	Coag. Test	H ₂ S Test	Meth. Red	Urea Test	VP Test	TSIA Test	Oxid. Test	Sugar fermentation		
													Glucose	Mannitol	Maltose
Results of biochemical tests	-ve rod	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve
Colony morphology	Circular convex, smooth colonies with green metallic sheen on EMB agar														

Legends:

EMB: Eosin Methylene Blue

VP: Voges Proskauer

TSIA: Triple Sugar Iron agar medium

3.3 Antibiotics Sensitivity/Resistance Profiles of the *E. coli* Isolates

Figure 2 indicates the antibiotics susceptibility profiles of *E. coli* isolated from cow dung, river water and human diarrheal samples from Okigwe. The results indicated that each of the antibiotics used against the isolates from the locations exhibited varying zones of inhibitions. On comparison of the zones of inhibition to the guidelines of the Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (2017) to classify the isolates into resistant, intermediate and sensitive to each of the antibiotics, results showed that sensitivities of the isolates from each sample to the antibiotics used in this study were low. It was observed that out of 12 *E. coli* isolates obtained from cow dung in Okigwe zone, the highest percentage (41.7%) of the isolates that showed sensitivity was recorded with Ciprofloxacin, while they were all resistant to Augmentin, Ceftriaxone, Cefepime, and Aztreonam. In river water samples, the highest percentage (23.1%) of isolates also showed sensitivity to Ciprofloxacin, whereas isolates were resistant to Ceftriaxone, Cefepime and Aztreonam.

For human diarrheal samples, the highest percentage (26.7%) of sensitive isolates was also recorded with Ciprofloxacin. As well, the isolates were all resistant to Augmentin, Ceftriaxone, Cefepime, Aztreonam and Meropenem. Statistically, at $\alpha = 0.05$ there was no significant difference in the percentages of isolates that showed sensitivity to the drugs across the samples studied.

Report of a related study showed that out of 280 faecal specimens from children with diarrhea that were screened for *E. coli*, 19 (6.7%) EPEC isolates were found to be highly resistant to ampicillin (100%), trimethoprim (89.4%) and tetracycline (84.2%). However, the isolates were sensitive to ciprofloxacin (95%), ceftazidime (79.0%), ceftriaxone (84.2%), and amoxicillin-clavulanate (79.0%). ESBL was detected in three (3) isolates (Abba and Dutsinma, 2021). Because intestinal *E. coli* strains may act as a reservoir of antibiotic resistance genes, it is crucial to comprehend the antibiotic susceptibility of pathogens (Imdad et al., 2018).

Figure 2. Antibiotics susceptibility profiles of *E. coli* isolates in cow dung, river water and human diarrheal samples from Okigwe. **Legends:** Parameters with different lower case letters are significantly different; R = Resistant; I = Intermediate and S = Susceptible

3.4 Prevalence of β -Lactamase Resistance Enzymes in *E. coli* Isolates in Cow dungs

Results obtained revealed the expression of diverse β -lactamase resistance enzymes in the identified *E. coli* isolates obtained from different samples Okigwe zone, Imo State. Figure 3(a) shows the agarose gel electrophoresis showing the amplified CTX-M genes of *E. coli* isolates. Each of the isolates produced one band, all of which migrated to equal distance on the gel. Comparing with 100 bp ladder used, the size of each of the bands use found to be 550 bp. Lane 6 did not show any bands indicating lack of CTX-M gene in the isolate.

Figure 3(b) is the agarose gel electrophoresis showing the amplified TEM genes of the isolates. Similarly, it was observed that all the isolates produced only one band which migrated to the same distance from the well. Using 100 bp ladder,

the size of each of the bands formed was determined to be 400 bp. However, there was no bands in lanes 5, 7 and 8 which indicated absence of the gene. Figure 3(c) presents the agarose gel electrophoresis showing the amplified SHV genes. As well, only one band was found for each of the isolates studied. Extrapolating the size of each of the genes using 100 bp ladder, it was found to be 300 bp. However, lanes 7, 8, and 9 lacked the gene and did not produce any bands. According to a prior investigation, all 29 strains that tested negative for the VCA also tested negative for the *stx1* and *stx2* genes using PCR. The presence of both the *stx1* and *stx2* genes was detected in three of the eight strains that caused a CPE on Vero cell monolayers, but none of the 37 isolates produced amplicons when the *eaeA* PCR was performed (Kabiru et al., 2015).

Figure 3(a). Agarose gel electrophoresis showing the amplified CTX-M genes.

Lane 1, 3-5, 7-10 represents the CTX-M gene bands at 550 bp and L represents the 100 bp molecular ladder. (b) Agarose gel electrophoresis showing the amplified TEM genes. Lane 1-4, 6, 9 and 10 represents the TEM gene bands at 400 bp and L represents the 100bp molecular ladder. (c) Agarose gel electrophoresis showing the amplified

SHV genes. Lane 1-6 and 10 represent the SHV gene bands at 300 bp and L represents the 100 bp molecular ladder.

Figure 4 indicates the percentage occurrence of β -lactamase resistance enzymes in *E. coli* isolated from cow dungs, river water and human diarrheal

samples from Okigwe zone of Imo State. From the results obtained, all the isolates expressed the three studied β -lactamase resistance enzymes including CTX-M, TEM-1 and SHV-1. However, the prevalence of CTX-M and SHV-1 enzymes was comparatively highest in isolates from human diarrheal samples, with 38.5% and 23.1% prevalence, respectively. River water samples recorded the least prevalence for the two enzymes

with 15.4% and 7.7% respectively. On the other hand, highest prevalence of TEM-1 enzyme was found in *E. coli* from cow dungs with 33.3% while the least prevalence was recorded in isolates from human diarrheal samples. Statistical analysis of the results at $\alpha = 0.05$ revealed that there is no significant difference in the prevalence of the resistance enzymes across the three samples.

Figure 4. Occurrence of β -lactamase resistance enzymes in *E. coli* isolates in cow dungs samples. Parameters with different lower case letters are significantly different.

3.5 Prevalence of Virulence Genes in *E. coli* Isolates

Figure 5 is the multiplex agarose gel electrophoresis showing the genes for enteropathogenic pathotype of *E. coli*. From the gel, it was seen that lanes 5 and 6 produced bands indicating the presence of *eae* and *bfpA* genes of EPEC. Compared with the 100 bp ladder used the sizes of *eae* and *bfpA* EPEC genes were found to be 800 bp and 500 bp respectively. This revealed the presence of different virulence genes in the *E. coli* isolates in samples from Okigwe, Imo State. Figure 6 indicates the percentage occurrence of virulence genes in *E. coli* isolated from cow dungs, river water and human diarrheal samples from Okigwe. Virulence genes for EPEC were detected in isolates

from all the samples. The prevalence of *eae* and *bfpA* genes of EPEC was highest in isolates from both river water and human diarrheal samples, which equally recorded 30.8% and 38.5% prevalence respectively. Isolates from cow dung expressed the least prevalence of *eae* and *bfpA* genes with 25.9% and 16.7% respectively. However, statistical analysis of the results at $\alpha = 0.05$ revealed that there is no significant difference in their prevalence across the samples studied.

Figure 5. Multiplex agarose gel electrophoresis showing the enteropathogenic strain of *E. coli*. Lanes 5 and 6 (*eae* and *bfpA*) represent the EPEC strains

Figure 6. Occurrence of virulence genes in *E. coli* isolates in cow dungs, river water and human diarrheal samples from Okigwe. **Legends:** Parameters with different lower case letters are significantly different.

This corresponds with the report of a prior study which indicated that *E. coli* was recovered from all 46 psittacines tested. Three samples were positive for the *eae* and *bfpA* genes (918 bp and 325 bp fragments, respectively), which were identified as typical EPEC (Saidenberg et al., 2012). Also, another study used biochemical techniques to detect *E. coli* in 280 fecal specimens from children with diarrhea and 20 from healthy children. The

results showed that EPEC was found in 19 (6.7%) of the test samples but not in the control group. The most common EPEC serotype was O55: K59 (B5). The *eaeA* and *bfpA* genes were found in 15.7% and 31.6% of the EPEC isolates, respectively. A study reported that one isolate they studied had typical EPEC (*eaeA+*, *bfpA+*), whereas seven isolates had atypical EPEC (Abba and Dutsinma, 2021). In comparison to earlier reports, the prevalence of EPEC found in this study is higher. According to reports, the prevalence of diarrhea in children was 6.7% (Abba and Dutsinma, 2021), 15% in Abuja (Adebola et al., 2014), 15% in Maiduguri (Bukar et al., 2014), and 19.5% in Aba (Ome and Nonye, 2015). These variations could result from variations in the pathotype distribution both within and between the cities.

Severe diarrhea may result from intestinal mucosal lesions caused by the attaching and effacing *E. coli* (AEEC) pathotype. Intimin, an adhesin produced by the *eae* gene, mediates the adherence of *E. coli* to the epithelial cell membrane, which starts this process. The locus of enterocyte effacement, which is linked to enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC), a significant subset of diarrheagenic *E. coli*, contains this gene. The bundle-forming pilus structural gene (*bfpA*), which is important for the bacteria's initial interaction with the host cell, and intimin are characteristics of typical EPEC strains (Saidenberg et al., 2012). Numerous gastrointestinal infections that can harm both human and animal health are found in livestock. According to a recent study, five of the 15 primary gastrointestinal infections that induce zoonotic transmission in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) are responsible for over one million deaths each year (Delahoy et al., 2018). One of the main causes of microbial shedding into the environment (soil and water) is human and animal open defecation. According to Shrivastava et al. (2020), different microbial agents from the soil can contaminate adjacent communal sources of water, putting people and animals at risk.

4. CONCLUSION:

Although *Escherichia coli* are naturally occurring microflora in both human and animal digestive tracts, some strains have developed the capacity to cause a variety of illnesses. Because of its biphasic nature, *E. coli* may thrive in both the host and the environment in which it is discharged along with animal and human waste. Therefore, farmers who often use animal excreta and river water for various farming activities need to be more conscious of the possible presence of EPEC isolates that have shown great resistance to numerous drugs in the cow dungs and river water samples, as well as their possible exposures to them. It is anticipated that both governmental and non-governmental organizations will step up efforts to curb the increasing zoonotic spread of multidrug-resistant forms of EPEC.

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5. COMPETING INTERESTS:

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

6. AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS:

Korie, Maximus Chibuoyi designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Uwaezuoke, Joseph Chidi, Obiukwu, Charles E. and Gladys Onyenonachi managed the analyses of the study. Yongabi, Kenneth Achang, Ohalete, Chinyere Ngozi and Nnagbo, Pauline managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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